

SUPPORTING MARKET UPTAKE OF BUILDING-INTEGRATED PHOTOVOLTAIC TECHNOLOGIES WITH THE PVSITES PROJECT

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ABSTRACT: In the framework of increasingly demanding legislation related to energy performance in buildings, the integration of photovoltaic systems in the building skin offers many possibilities. However, a continuous development of the building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) market in the next years necessarily demands the compliance with strict requirements in terms of design flexibility, aesthetics, durability, cost reduction, grid integration, testing standards and operation & maintenance. Within this context, a European consortium of 15 partners is developing the H2020 PVSITES project, “BIPV technologies and systems for large-scale market deployment”. The project will demonstrate an ambitious set of BIPV solutions, specially tailored to provide a comprehensive and robust answer to market demands. This paper focuses on some of the major results achieved at the time of writing. These include a detailed BIPV market and regulatory framework analysis and recommendations for the standardization of BIPV products. Novel developments of glazed crystalline silicon modules for BIPV integration are presented, with both opaque and see-thru variations. Also included are the selection of a battery technology best suited for inclusion in a custom-made building energy management system (BEMS), as well as a BIM-compatible software tool to assist the design of BIPV projects.
Keywords: Building Integrated PV (BIPV), Cost reduction, R&D and Demonstration Programmes

1 PURPOSE OF THE WORK

1.1 Context for European BIPV

BIPV is currently a steadily growing market. Market analysts estimate a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 18.7% and a total of 5.4 GW installed worldwide between 2013 and 2019 [1]. Currently the BIPV market holds a market share of around 2% of the overall PV market. However, the “BIPV Technologies and Markets: 2015-2022” report forecasts that BIPV penetration will rise to a 13% penetration by 2022 [2].

The EU currently leads the worldwide BIPV market, with 41% of total installations, followed by the USA with 27%. One of the main drivers for BIPV market growth in the EU is the increasingly demanding legislation related to energy performance in buildings.

Despite this favorable framework, it is a fact that estimations of BIPV market growth have been subsequently overestimated in the past few years. A series of demands from the stakeholders that have not been properly addressed by the BIPV value chain are probably the cause for this deviation. These key requirements are mainly related to:

- Flexibility in design
- Aesthetical considerations
- Lack of digital tools integrating PV and building performance at the earliest stage of a project to provide best bioclimatic design and financial options
- Lack of demonstration of long-term reliability of the technology
- Compliance with legal regulations
- Smart interaction with the grid
- Cost effectiveness

1.2 Project objectives

Within this context, the objective of the ongoing EU funded PVSITES project is to drive BIPV technology to a large market deployment by a combined virtual and real demonstration of an ambitious portfolio of building-integrated solar technologies and systems, giving a forceful, reliable answer to the market requirements identified by the industrial members of the consortium in their day-to-day activity. As a consequence, high impact demonstration and dissemination actions will be accomplished in terms of cost-effective renewable energy generation, aesthetics in solar architecture, reduction of energy demands and smart energy management.

The ambition of this project is, therefore, to pave the way towards a BIPV global market uptake led by the European industry and the emergence of a robust supply chain generating economic growth and job opportunities. An industrial consortium including partners with international reputation in the photovoltaics, building-integrated photovoltaics, construction and energy service sectors, supported by several RTOs and BIM experts for Energy Modeling, has joined efforts to reach this challenging objective. A wide range of BIPV solutions are being virtualized, developed and demonstrated in terms of design, building integration, performance, energy management, operation and maintenance, deconstruction, recycling and cost effectiveness.

This demonstration activity is carried out in 6 representative buildings across Europe plus experimental buildings and outdoor test benches, covering different climates, building uses, architectural implementations and energy management models.

1.3 Scientific innovation and relevance

PVSITES has a large innovation potential based on the generation and demonstration of flexible, robust, and cost-effective BIPV module and energy management technologies, together with associated software tools to support the design process.

- The BIPV solutions based on high efficiency crystalline silicon (c-Si) BIPV modules will substantially reinforce the aesthetics, flexibility of design and high performance considerations. Different strategies based on occultation of metallic contacts, high efficiency back-contact solar cells, glass treatments and coatings for improved passive properties and framing systems compatible with XL format glazing units. In addition to this, a low-concentration solar control BIPV system will be demonstrated, providing improved performance in terms of electricity generation and reduction of cooling demands, giving place to an unprecedented case in BIPV.
- The BIPV solutions based on high efficiency flexible lightweight CIGS thin film solar modules are opening a new paradigm in cost effective BIPV applications. Monolithically interconnected flexible lightweight CIGS solar modules produced with a roll-to-roll manufacturing process can provide low production costs of solar modules (< € 0.50/W for a 100 MW plant) and open novel opportunities for applications on roofs and facades in energy efficient buildings with lower carbon footprint.
- The combination of innovative power conversion and energy management technologies will increase BIPV electricity utilization (self-consumption). Novel BIPV generation and local electrical demand forecasting tools will reduce storage system costs by means of a practical selection and sizing of electrical storage system for each use case. The required storage capacity will also be reduced by means of active load management tools. Overall the achieved effect will be a cost reduction of the self-consumed electricity, coupled to an increase in the efficiency, flexibility and robustness of power conversion systems.
- The software tool for the coupled simulation of BIPV elements and building energy performance is, as of today, one of the only tools in the market offering this integrated approach. BIM and Energy Modeling will support and guarantee architectural and engineering workflows, as data will be added and exchanged through virtual workspaces, and even directly connected to the manufacturers' databases.

2 FIRST RESULTS

The PVSITES project started in January 2016 and will reach its conclusion in June 2019. This section summarizes a selection of results from completed or still ongoing tasks related to the project, as of September 2017. More detailed information can be consulted in a series of public reports made available on the project website [3].

2.1 BIPV market and regulatory framework analysis

Every analysis on the current BIPV market situation shows that there are a series of demands from the stakeholders that have not been properly addressed by the industry. The PVSITES project was conceived from its early stages to address these critical aspects with a joint

action bringing together the different actors of the BIPV value chain.

A detailed market assessment has been one of the first accomplished targets of the project. The current BIPV markets, trends and regulatory framework have been analysed by project partners and mainly R2M Solutions and Acciona, together with the stakeholders' needs, from the global figures to a more detailed analysis of BIPV in Europe and a final focus on the 4 countries in which PVSITES demonstration activities are taking place (France, Switzerland, Belgium and Spain). The markets and stakeholders involved in BIPV-related industries have also been part of the study. To support information gathering a stakeholder survey was developed within the consortium and distributed to key market actors through different channels. It was for instance sent online to members of photovoltaic associations and of the IEA PVPS Task 15 on BIPV, and circulated at *ad hoc* events such as the EUPVSEC 2016.

The market analysis showed that the penetration of BIPV has been overestimated by most analysts in the past years, mainly due to an unforeseen price drop of regular PV which made it a more profitable business than BIPV. It is nevertheless expected that the global BIPV market will grow in the coming years. This growth will be more conservative in the period 2016-2018 and will likely increase faster in the following years. It must be noted that within the PV market, the BIPV technologies will probably remain a niche market with no more than 8% of the total PV shipments by 2020, reaching 5 GW by 2020 [4].

Europe and the USA are foreseen as the BIPV market leaders, with approximately 3.5B€ invested in each market every year. Regulations toward near zero energy buildings, better incentives schemes in some countries and citizen consciousness are the main drivers for the optimistic forecast for the BIPV economy in Europe [5].

Among the targeted countries, France and Switzerland are in a better position for a faster and higher penetration of BIPV. Specific feed-in-tariffs and tenders for BIPV along with a higher social awareness regarding environmental issues increase the opportunities for investments in BIPV, although a recent decrease in French feed-in tariffs has reduced financial profitability for future installations. On the other hand, Spain has faced a deep crisis in the solar renewable energy field which led to almost zero PV installations in the past years. A recovery is now to be expected, with the recent tendering of large PV installations to be completed in 2019-2020 and the adoption of new regulation favoring self-consumption of renewable energy in buildings, although this will depend on political and economic stability in the longer term. Belgium has known a similar but less drastic situation than Spain with a significant decrease in annual installed capacity for three consecutive years in 2012-2014. The yearly installation volume has slowly recovered since then despite a lack of specific incentives for BIPV, and future trends remain uncertain.

At the European level a planned update of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), expected to be voted in October 2017, will set more stringent requirements for member states to accelerate the transition towards nearly-zero-energy buildings (NZEBs), with a specific focus on renovating the existing building stock. Once implemented this new legislative framework is expected to be favorable to BIPV installations.

The worldwide BIPV market can be divided into three sub-markets: glass, non-glass roofing and non-glass walling. The non-glass roofing market is currently the biggest one and it will continue to lead the market in the future, reaching 10B€ per year in 2021. Therefore, this market is and should remain the most attractive, almost doubling the investments in the other two by 2020.

The stakeholder analysis performed within the PVSITES project further shows the need for better integration between BIPV actors to reduce complexity and costs in the value chain. Contractors, architects and BIPV manufacturers are the main stakeholders and a close collaboration among them will foster their synergies, bringing benefits to the rest of the actors involved in the BIPV market. The main obstacles to the uptake of BIPV in Europe identified by market actors are related to the high costs of BIPV solutions, combined with a perceived uncertainty on the energy performance and lifetime of the products, as shown in Figure 1. Design flexibility, product aesthetics and compliance with local regulations are also major requirements.

Figure 1: Ranking of most important challenges to the development of BIPV in Europe as perceived by the 35 respondents to a PVSITES questionnaire [4].

2.2 Standardization of BIPV elements

In order to be suitable for building integration, BIPV products have to demonstrate compliance with the regulations from the PV and construction sectors. BIPV modules must therefore comply with the electro-technical requirements as set out in the Low Voltage Directive 2006/95/EC [6] and, as construction products, the requirements from the Construction Products Regulation CPR 305/2011 [7] have to be fulfilled. The still ongoing development of a specific and complete standardization context for BIPV elements, however, is one of the barriers affecting the market uptake of the technology.

The recently developed standard EN 50583 addresses the standardization needs for BIPV modules and systems used as construction products. It establishes three hierarchic levels of requirements for BIPV modules. The top level includes the relevant requirements for all kinds of PV modules, regardless of their technology and composition and the requirements for all technologies but depending on whether the modules do contain glass or not. The second level provides the requirements for glass and non-glass based modules, regardless of their location in the building but as a function of their backsheet material for the non-glazed ones. The third level applies only to glazed modules, and establishes differentiated requirements as a function of their location within the building.

BIPV products must also comply with the specific standards and regulations in the country of use. Depending

on the considered country, insurance applications, town planning rules (zoning regulation regarding colors, building shape...) and national building codes (fire, acoustic, thermal...) must also be met.

Taking all these aspects into account, the PVSITES consortium conducted an in-depth analysis of the standardization needs applicable to the project developments [8]. The results have shown that the EN 50583 standard provides a good reference though not all relevant requirements are covered and, in some cases, adaptations of tests or proposals of complementary standard tests are necessary. As an example, for low concentration BIPV products and curved glass/glass products in the PVSITES project, specific recommendations were proposed in order to adapt standard tests conditions to their configuration and properties. To ensure performance and long term reliability, standard test sequences were defined for each BIPV product and inverter developed within the project.

2.3 Crystalline silicon BIPV products

A large portfolio of products based on crystalline silicon (c-Si) and flexible thin film CIGS technologies is undergoing development within the PVSITES project. This paper will focus on the presentation of c-Si products as the CIGS products are expected to be fully developed at later stages.

One of the main constrains for BIPV market acceptability constrains is that most c-Si photovoltaic solutions show visible cell busbars and string L-interconnections. These metallic strips are necessary to harvest the electrical production occurring in the individual solar cells (busbars) and to connect the cells to each other within the modules (L-interconnections), but alter the otherwise homogenous aspect of the products. PVSITES partner Onyx Solar has therefore followed different strategies for the development of two generations of opaque c-Si glass-glass modules with hidden bus bars and L-interconnections [9]. Two product generations have been developed, as shown in Figure 2:

- 1st generation: Use of black plastic sheets compatible with glass lamination to hide the L- interconnections and use of black frit patterned rear glazing.
- 2nd generation: Use of black plastic sheets to hide the L-interconnections, implementation of black conductive ribbons and use of black frit patterned rear glazing to obtain a fully opaque solution.

Figure 2: Glazed c-Si modules with hidden bus bars and L interconnections (1st and 2nd generations shown left and right, respectively) [9].

For specific building solutions such as skylights and curtain walls, the decision maker is looking for certain light transmission values. For these cases, a compromise between cell density providing the see-thru degree, efficiency and aesthetical added value should be found. Attending to these needs, Onyx Solar has implemented back-contact solar cells within the photovoltaic glazing design [10].

Onyx Solar has also analysed potential glazing treatments compatible with BIPV technology, such as self-cleaning, mass coloured glass, frit patterned glass, reflective coatings and low-emissivity (low-E) coatings, in order to understand their effects on the BIPV glazing and the improvement generated on the passive properties of c-Si BIPV units [11]. A set of prototypes was manufactured based on this work, as shown in Figure 3.

The cost competitiveness of these newly-developed glazed c-Si modules has been analysed by the manufacturer [9,10]. Onyx Solar estimates end-user final prices in the range of 275-315 €/m² once commercial production starts. These price levels enable payback times of complete BIPV systems on the order of 5-12 years, depending on local contexts and project specifics.

Figure 3: Samples of c-Si based products with colour reflective (top), mass coloured glass and low-E treatments (bottom) for improved passive properties [11].

Framing systems suitable for the integration of extra-large and large thickness BIPV units in curtain walls, vertical facades and skylights have furthermore been defined and prototyped [12]. All above mentioned-products will be subjected to indoor validation testing to ensure their safety and reliability. A few of them will then be installed at the project's demonstration sites (see Section 2.5).

2.4 New inverter and BEMS technology

At system level, a combination of flexible and high efficiency grid interface and new building energy management strategies is under preparation. This work includes the demonstration of:

- A new planner tool to optimize the use of selected batteries for each use case, reducing the cost per unit of energy served (€/kWh that passes through the batteries).
- New power conversion designs (low-cost and high efficiency PV inverter with DC coupled storage system and a low-cost and robust PV inverter based on Silicon Carbide - SiC - technology), to enhance the conversion efficiency of the whole system.
- A novel low cost and reliable 24-hours-ahead forecasting tool, to develop innovative energy management strategies increasing overall economic performance.
- The integration of active load management tools, to reduce required storage capacity.

Work on the building energy management systems (BEMS) started with an analysis of commercially available electricity storage technologies and the recommendation of the most suitable one for the project's objectives. This documented comparison involved a series of tests by project partner CEA-INES [13]. The tested batteries were based on the aqueous sodium-ion (SI), lithium-iron-phosphate / graphite (LFP/G) and lithium-iron-phosphate / lithium-titanate (LFP/LTO) technologies. The investigated battery parameters included energy density, charge and discharge rates at different temperatures, cycle life testing under different charge/discharge conditions and thermal stability (for lithium-ion batteries). Lithium-iron-phosphate batteries were identified as the most suitable for electricity storage in BIPV applications due to superior discharge rates. Among LFP batteries, the testing campaign recommended the choice of LFP/G over LFP/LTO due to lower costs (370 €/kWh for LFP/G compared to 2055 €/kWh for LFP/LTO).

2.5 Demonstration activities

The developed BIPV products, inverters and BEMS will be implemented and tested over six demonstration sites and two test sites, representing a variety of building types and located in different European locations and climates. Six different building types are covered with the objective of testing the PVSITES products under as much different architectural integrations as possible and with different electrical requirements and load balance situations. This will considerably increase the use cases and strategies in which the products will be validated. Monitoring systems have been installed at each demonstration site to precisely track performance before and after the implementation of the PVSITES products. This includes both the energy production or storage and the improvements brought as a constructive element. The International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPVMP) methodology is being used to ensure the quality of the measurement and validation of the results. In the next page Table I summarizes preliminary information about the expected demo sites, as the exact implementation plans are still under definition. Implementation at the demonstration sites will be paired with training courses for installers, while guided visits will be offered after the commissioning phase.

Table I: Preliminary overview of the PVSITES demonstration sites and respective BIPV installations.

	Single House	Educational building	Carport
(1)	FormatD2	Flisom	Flisom
(2)	Stambruges Belgium	Geneva Switzerland	Zürich Switzerland
(3)	Roofing shingles (CIGS on steel)	Large tiles on façade (CIGS on metal substrate)	Roof tiles (CIGS on metal sheets)
(4)	Flisom	Flisom	Flisom
(5)	SSW	E + W	Horizontal
(6)	75 m ²	136 m ²	180 m ²
(7)	8 kWp	4 + 8 kWp	16 kWp
	Industrial building	Apartment building	Office building
(1)	Cricursa	Vilogia	Tecnalia
(2)	Barcelona Spain	Wattignies France	San Sebastián Spain
(3)	Large roofing shingles (CIGS on metal substrate)	Ventilated façade (c-Si modules with hidden bus bars)	Ventilated façade (Glass-glass back contact c-Si cells)
(4)	Flisom	Onyx Solar	Onyx Solar
(5)	Horizontal	SSE	SSE
(6)	225 m ²	130 m ²	170 m ²
(7)	19 kWp	20 kWp	10 + 10 kWp

(1) PVSITES partner responsible for the demonstration site
 (2) Location
 (3) BIPV product demonstrated
 (4) Manufacturer
 (5) Orientation of BIPV modules
 (6) Surface area of BIPV modules
 (7) Installed PV power

2.6 Integrated simulation software tools

Finally, aimed at the earliest design phases of BIPV projects, a BIM-compatible and bioclimatic simulation software for the joint prediction of photovoltaic and building energy performance is being finalized by project member CADCAMation, as illustrated in Figure 4. BIM technology makes possible the early virtualization of all BIPV products created during the project into the architectural design of buildings. 3D geometry properties coupled with optical and thermal modeling will feed-in the engineering workflow with contextual data, optimizing the technical integration into the building skin and the coupling with thermal comfort simulations.

The work-in-progress software will answer a series of well-defined customer needs and strengthens decision processes, by providing the following features:

- A specific design tool for PVSITES products integration into the building skin, as a specialized plugin into BIM ready BIPV software.
- Libraries of standardized BIPV products and related PVSITES solutions, turned into BIM components.

- Compliance of BIPV products with legal requirements demonstrated from the earliest feasibility study through “BIM constraints check” services.
- Bridging the gap between architects, engineers and PV manufacturers as BIM is first and foremost a collaborative methodology generating collaborative workspaces.

A pre-commercial version of the user-friendly software was released in September 2017 and can be accessed on the project website [3].

Figure 4: 3D visualisation of yearly solar irradiance on a building façade with the PVSITES software tool [3].

3 CONCLUSIONS

Between January 2016 and September 2017, the activities of the PVSITES consortium have contributed towards a greater market uptake of BIPV technologies by fulfilling some of the most relevant demands from stakeholders. The first project results presented in this paper will be refined in the months ahead and together with the rest of the work in progress, will culminate in the demonstration of an ambitious portfolio of BIPV systems in real buildings by the summer 2019. The expected impacts are classified in several categories:

- Market impacts, through a relevant increase in total BIPV installed capacity in the period 2020-2024 and with a payback time of 5-7 years at maximum.
- Increased competitiveness of EU industry with a very relevant associated job creation.
- Environmental impacts from additional installed power due to PVSITES, with a reduction of overall CO2 emissions 12% higher than in the business-as-usual case.
- Early integration of BIPV elements in building projects through BIM-based software modeling.
- Smart management of the building energy demand and of the electricity injection into the grid, thus reducing potential grid stress and the need to reinforce the grid.
- Increased stakeholder awareness and acceptance of BIPV as a consequence of high impact demonstration and targeted dissemination actions.

Regular project news can be consulted on the project website [3].

4 REFERENCES

[1] Transparency Market Research, “Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) Market: Global Industry Analysis, Size, Share, Growth, Trends and Forecast, 2013 – 2019”, 2014.
 [2] n-tech Research, “BIPV technologies and markets: 2015-2022,” 2015.

- [3] PVSITES project website, www.pvsites.eu
- [4] PVSITES Report, “BIPV market and stakeholder analysis and needs”, 2016.
- [5] PVSITES Report, “European regulatory framework for BIPV”, 2016.
- [6] Official Journal of the European Union, “Directive 2014/35/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council”, 2014.
- [7] Official Journal of the European Union, “Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council”, 2011.
- [8] PVSITES Report, “Standardization needs”, 2016.
- [9] PVSITES Report, “Opaque photovoltaic glazing solutions based on crystalline silicon with hidden busbars and L interconnections”, 2017.
- [10] PVSITES Report, “See-through photovoltaic glazing solutions based on back contact solar cells”, 2017.
- [11] PVSITES Report, “Samples of crystalline silicon based photovoltaic glazing products for indoor validation tests”, 2017.
- [12] PVSITES Report, “Prototypes of framing systems compatible with XL format and large thickness photovoltaic glazing units”, 2017.
- [13] PVSITES Report, “Recommendations on storage systems for BIPV systems”, 2017.

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